

Interview's Protocol for the System Requirement Validation

Interview Script

1. General Objective of the Interviews:

- Identify the challenges that visually impaired students face towards the creation of UML diagrams in computing.

2. Specific Objectives of the Interviews:

- Identify what are the main hardships faced by visually impaired students;
- Identify possible improvements for the prototype that is going to be developed to aid visually impaired students.

3. Target Audience:

- Visually impaired students in computing higher education and visually impaired developers in general;

4. Interview guidelines:

- The interview will be carried out in a semi-structured way, allowing the interviewee to answer the questions in any way they wish;
- The interviewer should not interrupt the interviewee;
- The interviewer should not influence in the interviewee's response;
- Biases should be reduced and judging the interviewee's responses should be avoided.

5. During the Interview:

- Introduction of the interviewer;
- Inform the research objectives to the interviewee;
- Describe how the prototype of the proposed tool will be;

- Ask the interviewee if he has any questions;
- Inform that the interview will be recorded, as well as the confidentiality rules;
- Make the questions in the script.

6. After the Interview:

- Ask for feedback regarding the questions asked to the interviewee;
- Inform that the interviewee will receive the research artifact, following the accessibility criterias, after the end of the study via e-mail;
- Inform that the recording is ending.